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Porous Bleed Boundary Conditions for Supersonic Flows with & without Shock-Boundary Layer Interaction

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Abstract

This paper aims to evaluate the prediction accuracy of various porous bleed models on two flow cases of particular interest for supersonic applications: turbulent boundary layer bleeding and control of shock-boundary layer interactions. A thorough literature review was conducted to select the most relevant models. The models were then implemented as suction/blowing boundary conditions in the in-house compressible RANS solver *elsA* with a flexible approach based on source terms. Reference simulations with the holes considered in the computational domain were conducted in order to assess the models' prediction capabilities. Two kinds of comparison were performed. In the first step, physical data (e.g., pressure, bleed mass flux) were extracted from the reference simulation and compared to the model predictions for the same conditions. In the second step, we performed RANS simulations using the various models as boundary conditions on a porous patch. Significant discrepancies between reference data and model predictions are highlighted, particularly for the bleed mass flux and velocity profiles, for which too high levels of momentum are predicted in the wall vicinity. This effect is supposedly attributed to the continuous application of transpiration over the patch. This has been shown to lead to an over-estimation of the bleed effectiveness for the shock-boundary interaction flow case. In addition, reference simulations conducted in this study show

that the diameter of the bleed holes influences the flow, which the existing porous bleed models do not consider. The outcome of this work, which highlights the deficiencies of state-of-the-art models, suggests the need to elaborate more advanced modeling for accurate prediction of both porous bleed performance and effect on the controlled flow.

Keywords: Porous bleed, Shock-boundary layer interaction, Flow control, Suction and blowing boundary condition

1 Nomenclature

Latin symbols

A	=	Area
a, b	=	Coefficients
C_D	=	Discharge Coefficient
c_b	=	Empirical constant
c_p	=	Heat capacity for constant pressure
D	=	Hole diameter
\mathcal{D}	=	Diagnostic function
d	=	Wall distance
H	=	Boundary layer shape factor
L	=	Hole length
L_w	=	Plate length
M	=	Mach number
\dot{m}	=	Mass flow rate
p	=	Static pressure
q	=	Mass flux
$Q_{sonic,w}$	=	Surface sonic flow coefficient
R_s	=	Specific gas constant (air)
Re	=	Reynolds number
s	=	Solidity
T	=	Static temperature
TR	=	Throat ratio
\vec{u}	=	Velocity vector
v	=	Transpiration velocity
x, y, z	=	Cartesian coordinates

Greek symbols

α	=	Angle of attack
α_R	=	Relaxation factor
Δ	=	Difference
δ ; δ_{99}	=	Boundary layer thickness
δ_1	=	Displacement thickness
δ_2	=	Momentum thickness
ε	=	Coefficient
η	=	Flow efficiency
γ	=	Heat capacity ratio
μ	=	Dynamic viscosity
ν	=	Kinematic viscosity
Ω	=	Vorticity
ϕ	=	Porosity level
φ	=	Contraction factor
ρ	=	Density
τ	=	Shear stress

Subscripts

bl	=	Bleed
c	=	Cell
e	=	Boundary layer edge
h	=	Hole
i	=	Incompressible
pl	=	Plenum
pl, ex	=	Plenum exit
$sonic$	=	Sonic
t	=	Total
w	=	External wall

2 Introduction

The porous bleed is a proven technology to mitigate the flow separation caused by shock-boundary layer interactions and stabilize the shock system. Generally, it is placed below the shock foot, e.g., in supersonic air intakes. Typical bleed regions consist of plates with hundreds of small holes covering a cavity (see Figure 1). The removal of air from the cavity generates a lower pressure than in the external flow, which enables the removal of the low-momentum air in the boundary layer of the external flow. Thus, the boundary layer profile upstream of the shock becomes fuller and more resistant to adverse pressure gradients. Besides, the air inside the separated region downstream of the shock is sucked away.

Although the working principle of porous bleeds is quite simple, predicting the extracted mass flow rate and the effect on the flow field is still challenging. Thus, the design of porous bleed regions in industrial cases is problematic

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as numerical simulations, including all the bleed holes in the size of the displacement thickness of the boundary layer [1], are too expensive. In the past, multiple porous bleed models have been introduced [1–8]. Generally, these models can be directly applied as a boundary condition at the wall without the need to refine the mesh.

Fig. 1: Schematic of a porous bleed

In the past, only a few investigations compared porous bleed boundary conditions with full simulations, including the holes [9–12]. Akatsuka et al. [9] compared the model of Harloff and Smith [1] with wind tunnel experiments using different hole diameters and single-hole simulations. They proved an influence of the ratio of hole diameter to boundary layer thickness, which is not considered in the model. Hamed et al. [10] and Wukie et al. [11] observed thinner and fuller boundary layer profiles downstream of the bleed region by applying the model of Slater [6] compared to three-dimensional reference simulations. However, more research is required to investigate the reason for this drawback.

In this study, we aim to evaluate the prediction accuracy of selected porous bleed models, as it may help the community better select a suitable model for their application. The models are implemented as a boundary condition in a compressible Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) solver. Reference simulations for two different flow cases are performed as a benchmark, and the bleed models are evaluated on their basis in different steps. First, the models are compared a posteriori using the extracted data from the reference simulations. After that, RANS simulations with the bleed models implemented as a boundary condition are conducted to compare their performance. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first comprehensive comparison of state-of-the-art bleed models.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 3 introduces the selected bleed models, their validity range and the implementation approach. The reference simulations that serve as the benchmark for the comparison are presented in

Section 4. The bleed models are evaluated in the next section based on an a posteriori comparison and within the RANS solver as implemented boundary condition. Our conclusions are drawn in the final section.

3 Porous bleed models

In the following, eight selected models are presented in the order of their publication date. All equations have been transcribed in the notation shown in Figure 1 to facilitate the comparison. For the application of the models, the holes are not modeled, but a suction/blowing boundary condition is applied on all cell faces, defined as the bleed region or bleed patch. All quantities extracted or computed on these faces are denoted as wall quantities (subscript w). By contrast, the subscript bl designates the bleed flow properties inside the bleed holes. An important step is the conversion of the bleed quantities into wall quantities using the porosity level ϕ . Thus, the bleed area

$$A_{bl} = \underbrace{\phi A_w}_{\text{Boundary condition}} = \underbrace{\sum A_h}_{\text{Reality}} \quad (1)$$

can be computed by correcting the wall area A_w using the porosity level. While the bleed mass flow rate [kg/s] equals the mass flow rate passing the wall $\dot{m}_{bl} = \dot{m}_w$, the wall mass flux [kg s/m²] given by

$$q_w = \phi q_{bl} \quad (2)$$

is lower than the bleed mass flux q_{bl} . This correction is required as the blowing and suction are applied on the whole patch and not locally distributed as in reality, where the bleed area corresponds to the sum of all holes areas A_h .

Only the final equations, as implemented in our solver, are shown for the presentation of the bleed models. See the corresponding reference for more details regarding the models and their derivations. Typically, bleed models have a wall transpiration flow velocity v_w or wall mass rate \dot{m}_w as the outcome. In this paper, all model outputs are converted into the wall mass flux for later application in the boundary condition.

$$q_w = \dot{m}_w / A_w = v_w \rho_w \quad (3)$$

3.1 Model description

3.1.1 Abrahamson and Brower (1988)

The bleed model introduced by Abrahamson and Brower [2] is an analytical approach to compute the transpiration flow velocity across the plate based on

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the isentropic mass flow rate. The transpiration velocity is expressed as

$$v_w = \frac{c_b p_{pl} \phi}{\rho_w T_w} \sqrt{\left(\frac{p_w}{p_{pl}}\right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} \left[\left(\frac{p_w}{p_{pl}}\right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right] \frac{2\gamma}{R_s(\gamma-1)}} \quad (4)$$

for unchoked holes or as

$$v_w = \frac{c_b p_{pl} \phi}{\rho_w T_w} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{R_s} \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2}\right)^{\frac{-(\gamma+1)}{2(\gamma-1)}}} \quad (5)$$

for choked flow with a pressure ratio $p_{pl}/p_w < 0.528$. The variable c_b is an empirically derived constant required to obtain agreement with the experiments of Hingst and Tanji [13]. Those experiments have been carried out for free-stream Mach numbers $M = 2.47$ and $M = 1.98$ and an oblique shock-boundary layer interaction with a hole diameter of $D = 3.17$ mm and a porosity level of $\phi = 34.8\%$.

3.1.2 Poll et al. (1992)

The bleed model of Poll et al. [3] is also an analytical model to compute the transpiration flow, which does not consider external flow. Here, the flow through the individual holes is assumed to be laminar and incompressible. The relation between pressure drop $\Delta p = p_w - p_{pl}$ and mass flow rate is expressed as

$$\frac{\Delta p D^2}{\rho \nu^2} \left(\frac{D}{L}\right)^2 = 40.7 \frac{\dot{m}_{bl}}{\mu t} \left(1 + 0.05 \frac{\dot{m}_{bl}}{\mu L}\right). \quad (6)$$

Finally, we obtain the bleed mass flow rate by finding the root of (quadratic) equation 6.

3.1.3 Harloff and Smith (1996)

The model of Harloff and Smith [1] is an approach to model the flow through a single hole or slot using the conservation of mass, momentum, and energy as well as empirical relations. Here, only the equations for a 90-degree hole are presented. The idea is to model the discharge coefficient of the hole for different geometries depending on the local flow conditions. Therefore, discharge coefficient correctors for the pressure effect ΔC_D^P , the effect of flow separation ΔC_D^S , and the length-to-diameter effect $\Delta C_D^{L/D}$ are added to the initial discharge coefficient.

$$C_D = C_D + \Delta C_D^P + \Delta C_D^S + \Delta C_D^{L/D} \quad (7)$$

The discharge coefficient depends on the Mach number at the boundary layer edge M_e (see Figure 1).

$$C_D = C_{D,i} + \Delta C_D^{L/D} \quad \text{if } M_e = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$C_D = \frac{C_{D,i} + C_D^B}{2} \quad \text{if } 0 < M_e < 0.6 \quad (9)$$

$$C_D = C_D^B \quad \text{if } M_e \geq 0.6 \quad (10)$$

Without external flow, the incompressible discharge coefficient $C_{D,i} = 0.82$ is considered and corrected according to the length-to-diameter ratio. For Mach numbers $M_e < 0.6$, the discharge coefficient is based on the incompressible discharge coefficient and the discharge coefficient of Bragg [14], which in turn is a function of the pressure ratio and the incompressible discharge coefficient $C_D^B = CD(C_{D,i}, p_{pl}/p_w)$. For higher Mach numbers, only the discharge coefficient of Bragg [14] is applied.

The correction of the pressure effect is only taken into account for high Mach numbers $M_e > 0.84$ and pressure ratios $p_{pl}/p_w > 0.5$ when the presence of internal flow separation is assumed:

$$\Delta C_D^P = -0.46 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} - 0.5 \right) \quad \text{if } \begin{cases} M_e > 0.84 \\ \frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} > 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta C_D^P = 0 \quad \text{else} \quad (12)$$

Moreover, depending on the Mach number M_e , flow separation in the holes is considered with the trend of a lower corrector ΔC_D^S for higher Mach numbers.

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.1M_e \quad \text{if } M_e \leq 0.6 \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.06 - 0.4(M_e - 0.6) \quad \text{if } 0.6 < M_e \leq 1.0 \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.22 - 0.217(M_e - 1.0) \quad \text{if } 1.0 < M_e \leq 1.6 \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta C_D^S = -0.35 \quad \text{if } M_e > 1.6 \quad (16)$$

The last considered effect is the length-to-diameter ratio effect. For long holes, the friction losses are assumed to be higher, leading to an increased discharge coefficient for lower ratios:

$$\Delta C_D^{L/D} = 0.08 \quad \text{if } L/D < 3 \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta C_D^{L/D} = 0 \quad \text{if } L/D \geq 3 \quad (18)$$

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For the computation of the bleed mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl} , the sonic mass flow rate \dot{m}_{sonic} needs to be determined first. Therefore, the sonic area

$$A_{sonic,w} = \phi A_w \frac{216}{125} M_{bl} (1 + 0.2M_{bl}^2)^{-3} \quad (19)$$

is computed with the hole exit Mach number

$$M_{bl} = \sqrt{5 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \right)^{-2/7} - 5}. \quad (20)$$

By knowing the sonic area, the sonic mass flow rate is calculated as follows:

$$\dot{m}_{sonic,w} = A_{sonic,w} p_w \left(\frac{\gamma}{R_s T_w} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{-\gamma + 1}{2(\gamma - 1)}}. \quad (21)$$

Finally, the bleed mass flow rate can be computed.

$$\dot{m}_w = C_D \dot{m}_{sonic,w} \quad (22)$$

The model of Harloff and Smith [1] has been calibrated and validated on different experimental datasets [15, 16].

3.1.4 Doerffer and Bohning (2000)

Doerffer and Bohning [4] provide a porous bleed model based on the experimental data generated in the EUROSCHOCK project [17]. The tested perforated plates have small hole diameters from 0.085 mm to 0.325 mm and porosity levels ranging from 2.27% to 24.9%. It should be noted that the porosity stated by Doerffer and Bohning [4] is an aerodynamic (measured) porosity, which is used because of manufacturing tolerances resulting in slightly differing hole sizes and hence, porosity levels. Therefore, a dependency between aerodynamic porosity and pressure drop without external flow was found, and all plates were calibrated using this relation. Moreover, the validation of the model with an external flow was performed using a plate with a hole diameter of $D = 0.185$ mm and a low porosity level of $\phi = 5.05\%$ or $\phi = 5.30\%$ depending on the installation direction. They found a relation between the pressure difference Δp across the plate and the effective (bleed) Mach number in the holes. Suction and blowing are distinguished because the suction mass flow rate was observed to be reduced for increasing external flow velocities.

In the case of suction, the following relation is applied:

$$\frac{p_w - p_{pl}}{p_w} = M_{bl}^{0.55} \left[\left(\frac{1}{1.2} \right)^{\frac{1}{0.55}} + 25 \left(\frac{|\tau_w|}{\rho_h v_{bl}^2} M_{bl} \right)^{\frac{1}{1.52}} \right]. \quad (23)$$

Here, the wall shear stress τ_w is used to quantify the external flow velocity. Its value is normalized by the dynamic pressure of the flow in the hole. In contrast, the external flow is not considered in the case of blowing. Hence, the pressure difference is only a function of the effective (bleed) Mach number:

$$\frac{p_{pl} - p_w}{p_{pl}} = M_{bl}^{\frac{1}{0.55}} \left[\left(\frac{1}{1.2} \right)^{\frac{1}{0.55}} \right] \quad (24)$$

The holes are assumed choked for a Mach number of $M_{bl} \geq 0.57$. This value is set as a limiter in the model.

Finally, with the knowledge about the hole Mach number, the mass flow rate is computed

$$\dot{m}_w = \phi A \rho_h \frac{M_{bl} \sqrt{\gamma R_s T_0}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M_{bl}^2}} \quad (25)$$

with T_0 being T_w for suction and T_{pl} for blowing.

3.1.5 Frink et al. (2003)

The boundary condition introduced by Frink et al. [5] uses the porous surface model of Bush [18] for screen losses to simulate the transpiration flow through a porous wall in the case of passive control. However, its definition also enables the use in an active mode by setting a different plenum pressure. Three different states are defined in the equations, with the first state located upstream of the hole corresponding to the wall properties (subscript w), the second state associated with the throat inside the hole where the stream tube is the most contracted (subscript h), and the third state being downstream inside the cavity plenum corresponding to the subscript pl in the current nomenclature. The throat area inside the hole (A_h) is calculated

$$A_h = A_{pl} \underbrace{\varphi}_{\phi} (1 - s) \quad (26)$$

with the contraction factor φ and the solidity $s = 1 - \phi$. The contraction factor is based on an empirical relationship found by Bush [18] in the experimental data of Cornell [19]:

$$\varphi = \varphi_0 + 0.185(1 - \phi)^{1/4} \left(\frac{p_{t,h}}{p_h} - 1 \right) \quad (27)$$

$$\varphi_0 = \frac{0.04137}{1.0982 - \phi} + 0.57293 + 0.005786\phi \quad (28)$$

Thus, the contraction factor is purely based on the porosity ϕ and the reciprocal of the isentropic pressure ratio inside the holes, a function of the Mach number M_h .

In the following, only the equations considering flow from the external wall into the cavity plenum are regarded where the plenum pressure is smaller than the external wall pressure $p_{pl} < p_w$. In case of blowing, the plenum and wall states need to be swapped to obtain a flow into the domain. In the first step, the flow inside the hole throat is assumed to be choked ($M_h = 1$) to compute the maximum achievable mass flux through the holes. Therefore, the Mach number inside the plenum M_{pl} is iteratively calculated using the Newton approach:

$$\frac{\gamma + 1}{2} \left[\frac{1 + \gamma M_{pl}^2}{1 + \gamma \phi} \right]^2 \varphi^2 \phi^2 - M_{pl}^2 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_{pl}^2 \right) = 0 \quad (29)$$

Subsequently, the maximum mass flux in the plenum is computed using the static pressure and the total temperature T_t :

$$(\rho u)_{max} = \left(\sqrt{\gamma / (R_s T_t)} \right) p_{pl} M_{pl} \left[1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_{pl}^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (30)$$

If the flow is choked, $(\rho u)_w \geq (\rho u)_{max}$, the Mach number in the hole is set to $M_h = 1$, and the mass flux at the wall to $(\rho u)_w = (\rho u)_{max}$. If not, M_h is iteratively calculated.

$$M_h^2 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_h^2 \right) \left[\frac{1 + \gamma M_{pl}^2}{1 + \gamma M_h^2 \phi} \right]^2 \varphi^2 \phi^2 - \frac{R_s T_t (\rho u)_w^2}{\gamma p_{pl}^2} = 0 \quad (31)$$

It is essential to know that the contraction factor is a function of M_h , which is, in turn, computed using the contraction factor. Therefore, multiple iterations are required to converge to the final Mach numbers M_h and M_{pl} .

In the next step, the physical quantities at the wall are computed, starting with the total pressure $p_{t,w}$:

$$p_{t,w} = p_{pl} \frac{1 + \gamma M_{pl}^2}{1 + \gamma M_h^2 \phi} \left[1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_h^2 \right]^{\gamma / (\gamma - 1)} \quad (32)$$

The Mach number at the wall is iteratively solved as follows.

$$M_w^2 \left[1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_w^2 \right]^{-\frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1}} - \frac{R_s T_t (\rho u)_w^2}{\gamma p_{t,w}^2} = 0 \quad (33)$$

The static wall pressure is finally computed by knowing the total conditions and the Mach number:

$$p_w = p_{t,w} \left[1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_w^2 \right]^{-\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (34)$$

Since the wall pressure is directly extracted from the boundary interface inside the domain during the numerical computation, and the wall mass flux $q_w = (\rho u)_w$ is required, a further iterative calculation using the Newton method is needed to obtain the desired output. Please note that Equations 29, 31, and 33 are stated differently in the original publication because of an error in the isentropic flow relation. Non-consideration of these corrections increases the estimated mass flux by approximately one order of magnitude.

3.1.6 Slater (2012)

The bleed model of Slater [6] is an empirical model based on the supersonic experiments of Willis et al. [16] for the (C1) plate with a hole diameter of $D = 6.35$ mm and a porosity level of $\phi = 19.1\%$. The sonic flow coefficient, defined as

$$Q_{sonic,w} = \frac{\dot{m}_w}{\dot{m}_{sonic,w}} \quad (35)$$

is scaled with respect to wall conditions using the mass flow rate \dot{m}_w and the sonic mass flow rate for wall conditions:

$$\dot{m}_{sonic,w} = p_w \phi A_w \left(\frac{\gamma}{R_s T_w} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{-\gamma + 1}{2(\gamma - 1)}} \quad (36)$$

This scaling is applied to eliminate the dependency of the Mach number at the boundary layer edge from the equations. Otherwise, the extraction at the boundary layer edge would be required, which is complex and almost impossible for separated or distorted flows. The sonic flow coefficient for wall conditions quantifies the efficiency of the bleed device. The author proposed a quadratic curve fit to model the sonic flow coefficient

$$Q_{sonic,w} = -0.57 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \right)^2 + 0.6 \quad (37)$$

as a function of the pressure ratio of plenum pressure and external wall pressure.

3.1.7 Choe et al. (2020)

The model of Choe et al. [7] is a variation of the boundary condition of Slater [6]. Slater [6] assumes a wall pressure equal to the pressure on the boundary layer edge. By contrast, Choe et al. [7] take the effect of the flow expansion above the porous bleed region into account. Baurle and Norris [20] have already found an underestimation of the sonic flow coefficient using the bleed model of Slater [6] due to the missing consideration of the local flow expansion in the bleed region.

The new scaling of Choe et al. [7] leads to the new quadratic curve fit

$$Q_{sonic,w} = 0.6756 - 0.8086 \left(\frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \right)^2 + 0.1846 \frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \quad \text{if } \frac{p_{pl}}{p_w} \geq 0.2634 \quad (38)$$

$$Q_{sonic,w} = 0.6681 \quad \text{else} \quad (39)$$

by using the same validation data [16] as Slater [6].

3.1.8 Grzelak et al. (2021)

Grzelak et al. [8] defined the first bleed model based on a numerical database. Therefore, single-hole simulations without external flow were conducted. The simulations were validated against experiments by measuring the mass flow rate for three different porous plates up to choking conditions. The authors introduced the concept of modeling the flow efficiency η , which describes the flow losses across the plate. Using the flow efficiency, the Mach number at the hole outlet is computed

$$M_{bl} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma - 1} \left[\left(1 + \eta \left(\frac{p_w}{p_{pl}} - 1 \right) \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right]} \quad (40)$$

as a function of the pressure ratio from stagnation hole inlet pressure, which is equal to the wall pressure p_w for no external flow, to the static hole outlet pressure, here described by the plenum pressure p_{pl} .

By knowing the hole exit Mach number, the mass flow rate of the boundary condition is computed as:

$$\dot{m}_w = \phi A_w [p_{pl} + \eta(p_w + p_{pl})] \sqrt{\frac{\gamma M_{bl}^2}{R_s T_w \left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M_{bl}^2 \right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma-1}}} \quad (41)$$

The flow efficiency is expressed as

$$\eta = 0.429\phi - 0.01803 \frac{L}{D} + 0.64472, \quad (42)$$

which is a function of the porosity level ϕ and the length-to-diameter ratio L/D . The validation range goes from 4% to 10% for the porosity level and 1.5 to 8 for the length-to-diameter ratio.

3.2 Scope of application

For the control of shock-boundary layer interactions (see Figure 1), various aspects must be considered in modeling the porous bleed to guarantee an accurate prediction. For strong shock-boundary layer interactions, both sub- and supersonic flows must be controlled downstream and upstream, respectively, of the shock. Moreover, local blowing may occur due to the intense pressure gradient and shock instabilities, causing a higher static pressure in the plenum than in the supersonic region, which has to be considered in the modeling. Besides, low pressure ratios p_{pl}/p_w can lead to the choking of the holes.

Tab. 1 gives an overview of the range of validity for the different models. Furthermore, the table shows the additional input data required to compute the bleed mass flux. If no extra input is stated, the model only uses the static external wall pressure and plenum pressure, as well as the wall temperature and porosity level. These four quantities are required for each of these models.

Three of the selected models [2, 6, 7] are based on supersonic data only, which results in the consideration of compressible effects which are not necessarily present for subsonic flows. It is expected that the accuracy of the models is reduced for subsonic conditions. However, the governing equations of the models enable their use even for subsonic conditions, which is different from other models (e.g., Zhang et al. [21]) that are purely based on supersonic flow phenomena. On the contrary, the models of Poll et al. [3], Frink et al. [5], and Grzelak et al. [8] are validated without external flow. Consequently, flow separation in the front of the hole induced by any external flow is not considered. Harloff and Smith [1] introduced the only model relying on both supersonic and subsonic data. However, extracting the Mach number at the boundary layer edge M_e is required, complicating the implementation. The

Model	External flow		Choked holes	Blowing	Extra inputs
	Subsonic	Supersonic			
Abrahamson and Brower	-	✓	✓	-	-
Poll et al.	-	-	-	o	L/D
Harloff and Smith	✓	✓	✓	-	$L/D, M_e$
Doerffer and Bohning	✓	-	✓	✓	τ_w
Frink et al.	-	-	✓	o	-
Slater	-	✓	✓	-	-
Choe et al.	-	✓	✓	-	-
Grzelak et al.	-	-	✓	o	L/D

Table 1: Validated scope of application for the different models

model of Doerffer and Bohning [4] is validated up to $M = 0.9$ by using the wall shear stress as an indicator of the external flow magnitude.

Moreover, the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4] is the only model with a separate relation for blowing. For the models of Poll et al. [3], Frink et al. [5], and Grzelak et al. [8], no differentiation between blowing and suction (o) is made. Since the models of Slater [6] and Choe et al. [7] are based on a quadratic regression, pressure ratios $p_{pl}/p_w > 1$ lead to relatively high blowing rates.

In summary, none of the presented bleed models cover all possible situations that may appear in a shock-boundary layer interaction.

3.3 Implementation as a boundary condition

The application of the bleed models as a boundary condition allows a significant reduction of the mesh size by ignoring the real geometry of the bleed system, including the bleed holes and the cavity. Instead, the porous bleed was applied as a suction/blowing boundary condition on the wall. The Safran-ONERA finite-volume solver *elsA* [22] enables the use of the model of Poll et al. [3], which is implemented as a transpiration wall. The tangential wall velocity components are set to zero using this boundary condition, and only a wall-normal component is permitted. Since the boundary condition is not manipulatable, an approach using source terms has been applied, as explained in the following. This approach was validated with the implemented boundary condition of Poll et al. [3].

The solver *elsA* has an integrated interface that enables the run of *Python* codes with full access to the simulation data after (or before) a specific number of iterations, which allows the manipulation of the simulation. Thus, the bleed boundary condition was computed in *Python* and updated regularly. Therefore, several flow variables were extracted from the latest flow solution. The *Python* routine has access to all flow variables at all cell centers within the mesh and the values at the cell faces that are defined as bleed region.

Fig. 2: Extraction locations in the mesh

Figure 2 gives an overview of the extraction locations. The circles illustrate the cell centers, and the squares are the interfaces on the boundary condition. All positions where variables were extracted are marked in red. The red vertical

line symbolizes the extraction of the Mach number on the boundary edge required for the bleed model of Harloff and Smith [1]. The RANS-solver *elsA* offers multiple options to define the boundary layer edge to extract variables. Here, a diagnostic function

$$\mathcal{D} = d^a \|\Omega\|^b \quad (43)$$

with d being the wall distance and $\|\Omega\|$ the vorticity vector modulus was used [23]. The boundary layer thickness

$$\delta = \varepsilon d_{max} \quad (44)$$

is proportional to the wall distance where $D|_{d_{max}} = \max(D)$. The coefficients $a = 3.9$, $b = 1.0$, and $\varepsilon = 1.294$ were determined by Stock and Haase [23] for laminar flow. Even though Stock and Haase [23] also defined coefficients for turbulent velocity profiles, the laminar solution was applied as it is more robust than the turbulent and, thus, has a lower error in the case of suction or blowing.

The static wall pressure and temperature applied for the bleed models were extracted at the interfaces of the boundary condition (■). The wall shear stress required for the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4] was calculated using the flow properties in the first cell center (●) and the wall distance Δy :

$$\tau_w = \mu_c \frac{u_c}{\Delta y}. \quad (45)$$

Equation 45 was applied since the wall was defined as a viscous wall, and the dimensionless wall distance was $y^+ \approx 1$. The tangential velocity was assumed to be zero at the wall since the porosity level is relatively low.

The blowing and suction were applied to the first row of cells using source terms. The following source terms were adapted from Baurle and Norris [20] and added to the compressible Navier-Stokes equations.

$$\text{Continuity:} \quad \frac{q_w A_c}{V_c} \quad (46)$$

$$\text{Momentum:} \quad \frac{\vec{u} q_w A_c}{V_c} \quad (47)$$

$$\text{Energy:} \quad \frac{q_w c_p T_w A_c}{V_c} \quad (48)$$

The physical values applied in the source terms were directly extracted from the first cell centers (●). All bleed model outputs were converted to a wall mass flux q_w . The local mass flow rate was computed using the surface mass flux and the projected cell area A_c . All source terms were normalized using the local cell volume V_c .

A relaxation factor α_R was added to the computation of the wall mass flux

$$q_w^t = (1 - \alpha_R)q_w^{t-n} + \alpha_R q_w^t \quad (49)$$

to ensure robustness and to accelerate the simulation by updating the boundary condition only every n iterations.

Three options to set the working regime of the porous bleed for the computation of the bleed models are possible:

- ① Fixed plenum pressure p_{pl}
- ② Fixed mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl}
- ③ Fixed throat ratio TR .

① The fixation of plenum pressure is the classical way to define the working regime used by all existing models. ② The second option is the setting of a desired bleed mass flow rate. Therefore, the plenum pressure is iteratively updated until the used bleed model reaches the correct mass flow rate. The obtained plenum pressure is then used in the simulation. As the wall pressure varies with the computational iterations, this step has to be repeated with every update of the boundary condition. ③ The last option is setting the throat ratio

$$TR = \frac{A_{pl,ex}}{A_{bl}}, \quad (50)$$

which is the ratio of the plenum exit area $A_{pl,ex}$ and the bleed area A_{bl} . The flow in the plenum exit throat is supposed to be choked. With the assumption of a large cavity and, consequently, very low flow speed, the plenum pressure is assumed to be equal to the total pressure inside the cavity. Thus, the mass flow rate passing the choked nozzle

$$\dot{m}_{pl,ex} = \frac{p_{pl} A_{pl,ex}}{\sqrt{T_w}} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{R_s}} \left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{2} \right)^{-\frac{\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}} \quad (51)$$

is computed using the external wall temperature T_w . Hence, the mass flow rate leaving the cavity and the mass flow rate passing the porous plate can be determined as a function of the plenum pressure. Again, the plenum pressure is iteratively adjusted until the balance between these two flow rates is achieved [24]. The definition of a throat ratio facilitates the comparison between the three-dimensional simulation, where a choked nozzle fixes the mass flow rate, and the simulations with the bleed boundary condition. For this reason, the third option ③ was the default option used in this study.

4 Reference simulations

Three-dimensional RANS simulations serve as a benchmark to evaluate the selected bleed models. Therefore, two different flow cases of supersonic turbulent flow at a Mach number of $M = 1.6$ with and without shock-boundary layer interaction were chosen, and simulations were performed with bleed hole diameters of $D = 0.5$ mm and $D = 2.0$ mm. The hole diameter variation was chosen since it is an unconsidered parameter in existing modeling approaches. At the same time, it influences the effectiveness of the porous bleed system. More details about the reference simulations and the hole diameter influence can be found in Giehler et al. [25].

4.1 Numerical setup

The solver *elsA* was chosen with the turbulence modeled using the Spalart-Allmaras model with quadratic constitutive relation (QCR) [26]. The mesh, generated by the in-house mesh-generator *Cassiopee* [27], was fully parametric and structured, which allowed an easy variation of the geometry of the perforated plate. The mesh topology around the bleed holes is illustrated in Figure 3a.

Fig. 3: Mesh topology close to the porous wall; blue patches illustrate suction areas

This study investigates two porous plates with a porosity level of $\phi = 22.67\%$ and a length-to-diameter ratio of $L/D = 1$. The first plate had a hole diameter of $D = 0.5$ mm, and the second had a $D = 2.0$ mm diameter. The porous bleed was modeled by two half rows of holes in the spanwise direction and 40 ($D = 0.5$ mm) or 10 ($D = 2.0$ mm) holes in the streamwise direction. The bleed plenum had the size of the bleed region. Its exit was shaped like a nozzle to fix the mass flow rate under choked conditions (see Figure 1). In all conducted simulations, the throat ratio was set to $TR = 0.7$, which guaranteed suction through all bleed holes.

4.2 Supersonic turbulent boundary layer bleeding

The first investigated flow case is a Mach $M = 1.6$ flow over a flat plate, which could correspond to a bleed system installed upstream of a shock, aiming to thin the boundary layer. Figure 4 illustrates the investigated problem. The porous plate is located 40 mm downstream of the inlet and has a length of $L_w = 40$ mm. A turbulent supersonic profile from a flat plate simulation is provided as the inlet condition. The flow properties extracted 5 mm upstream of the porous plate are listed in Table 2. Dimensions and flow conditions are based on the ONERA S8Ch supersonic wind tunnel, where experimental investigations will be conducted.

Fig. 4: Schematic of the investigated numerical domain

Symmetry planes were applied on the sides of the domain, while a far-field boundary condition was used at the top. Supersonic outlet conditions were applied on the domain exit and the plenum outlet. Except for the plenum side walls, all walls were modeled by no-slip walls. Inside the cavity, slip walls were used to decrease the number of cells. The meshes had a size of 5.3 M. and 2.5 M. cells, respectively. A preliminary mesh convergence study was conducted and showed no change in the results for a finer resolved hole geometry on both bleed mass flow rate and downstream lying boundary layer profiles.

The flow fields of the reference simulations are shown in Figure 5. The working principle is clear: a transpiration flow through the porous plate into the cavity leads to air removal. Consequently, the boundary layer is thinned, and the flow is deflected toward the wall. At the beginning of the plate, an

M	p_t	T_t	Re_{δ_2}	δ_{99}	δ_1	δ_2	H
1.6	93 000 Pa	300 K	5415	4.20 mm	0.57 mm	0.42 mm	1.36

Table 2: Flow properties 5 mm upstream of the first bleed hole

Fig. 5: Mach number contour fields for the two reference simulations

expansion fan is provoked, and at the end, the trailing shock redirects the flow in the wall-parallel direction.

The three-dimensional simulations allow us to characterize local flow phenomena around the holes. The suction through the holes leads to a redirection of the flow into the hole, which provokes expansion waves as the affected flow is supersonic (clearly visible for $D = 2.0$ mm in Figure 5b). Further downstream, the barrier shock turns the flow around the rear edge of the hole. Hence, the boundary layer is locally thickened by an adverse pressure gradient. The larger the hole, the higher the mass flow rate passing the holes and, thus, the higher the momentum of the flow and the Mach number. This results in a higher shock intensity. Consequently, thinning the boundary layer is less effective for larger hole diameters [25].

The evolution of the physical quantities along the porous plate is presented in Figure 6 for both reference simulations. In Figure 6a, the external wall pressure is illustrated. The pressure is extracted on the solid wall around the holes and averaged over an area corresponding to the porosity level. Independently of the hole diameter, the wall pressure drops at the first hole because of the existence of the expansion fan at the beginning of the plate. Along the plate, the pressure increases as the boundary layer thinning is not linear, and the flow is deflected more and more in the wall-parallel direction [25]. At the end of the bleed region, the pressure rises because of the barrier shock downstream of the last hole.

More significant are the differences between the different hole diameters by observing the streamwise wall shear stress (see Figure 6b), extracted in

Fig. 6: Physical quantities along the porous plate

the same way as the wall pressure. The smaller the hole diameter, the larger the wall shear stress around the holes as the solid wall area between the holes becomes smaller. Thus, the area where the boundary layer can develop is reduced. This observation is relevant to the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4], which relies on the wall shear stress to calculate the bleed mass flow rate.

The bleed mass flux is locally extracted by averaging the momentum of the flow through the hole and visualized in Figure 6c for both reference simulations. For the small hole diameter, the mass flux is higher in the front of the plate and converges with the trend of the larger holes to the end. This is contrary to the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4], which predicts a lower mass flux for higher wall shear stresses.

4.3 Shock-boundary layer interaction control

The second flow case is dedicated to the control of a shock-boundary layer interaction. The Laval nozzle geometry of the S8Ch wind tunnel in Meudon is included in the domain. The physical properties 5 mm upstream of the bleed region are equal to those of the supersonic boundary layer bleeding (see Tab. 2). Moreover, a shock generator is added to the domain, which provokes an

Fig. 7: Computational domain for the shock-boundary layer interaction

oblique shock. This shock is non-regularly reflected at the wall, leading to a strong shock near the wall. The presence of the shock generator allows us to investigate the porous bleed in both supersonic and subsonic regimes.

In contrast to the first case, a subsonic inlet condition was applied as the acceleration to supersonic conditions is caused by the convergent-divergent nozzle. All wind tunnel walls were treated as no-slip walls. Both outlet boundary conditions were supersonic outlets, as in the first case.

The domain, including the shock generator, is schematically shown in Figure 7. The bleed region starts 40 mm downstream of the nozzle exit, where the leading edge of the shock generator is located. Its length is 40 mm to avoid any influence of the expansion fan caused by the rear edge of the shock generator. To obtain a shock system as drafted in Figure 7, the shock generator's angle of attack is $\alpha = 10^\circ$. Again, the reference simulations were performed for the hole diameters $D = 0.5$ mm and $D = 2.0$ mm with mesh sizes of 5.5 M. and 2.9 M. cells, respectively. Similarly to the previous flow case, a mesh convergence study was performed.

The Mach field contours for the uncontrolled (no porous bleed) and controlled cases with the shock-boundary layer interaction are visualized in Figure 8. A view in Figure 8a reveals the presence of a separation bubble below the lambda shock foot. The yellow line highlights the area of backflow. Downstream of the incident shock, the flow reattaches as the flow reaccelerates to supersonic conditions due to the expansion fan caused by the trailing edge of the shock generator.

In the controlled situations (see Figures 8b and 8c), the separation bubble and the lambda shock foot are removed. Thus, the incident shock moves downstream to the station $x \approx 68$ mm. Hence, approximately 70% of the plate controls a supersonic and 30% a subsonic flow. Similar to the previous flow case, a difference in the effectiveness of the control is noted. The smaller hole diameter leads to a higher flow momentum close to the wall, which results in a shock-boundary layer interaction closer to inviscid flow. The entire flow field is more homogeneous, and the effect of the local flow phenomena provoked by the holes is less significant.

Fig. 8: Mach number contour fields for the reference simulations with shock-boundary layer interaction and the uncontrolled case; yellow dashed line in (a) highlights upstream-oriented flow

The curves for the physical quantities, shown in Figure 9, lead to the same conclusion. For the small hole diameter of $D = 0.5$ mm, the shock-boundary layer is more inviscid, as indicated by the external wall pressure trend in Figure 9a. The pressure rise below the shock foot is steeper and less smeared than in the reference simulation, with the hole diameter being $D = 2.0$ mm.

The wall shear stress (see Figure 9b) indicates the same trend as the turbulent supersonic boundary layer bleeding. The smaller the hole diameter, the higher the wall shear stress. This effect is similar for super- and subsonic conditions. The bleed mass flux behaves similarly to the external wall pressure. It is

Fig. 9: Physical quantities along the porous plate with a shock-boundary layer interaction

increased for subsonic conditions downstream of the shock, where the pressure difference between the external wall and the cavity plenum is enhanced.

5 Evaluation of the bleed models

In this section, all bleed models introduced in Section 3 are compared to the reference simulations presented in Section 4. First, the models are a posteriori analyzed based on the physical properties obtained from the reference simulations. In the second step, the RANS predictions with the bleed models implemented in the boundary condition are compared to the reference data.

5.1 Supersonic turbulent boundary layer bleeding

5.1.1 A posteriori comparison

The extracted physical values from Section 4.2 are used for the a posteriori comparison. First, the surface sonic flow coefficient, as introduced by Slater [6], is computed for all selected bleed models for pressure ratios p_{pl}/p_w from

0 to 1, as shown in Figure 10. A sonic flow coefficient of one corresponds to a wholly choked hole cross-section and, thus, to a Mach number of $M_{bl} = 1$ inside the holes. A surface sonic flow coefficient higher than one is therefore regarded as unphysical as the bleed mass flow rate cannot be higher than the sonic mass flow rate.

Fig. 10: Predicted surface sonic flow coefficient $Q_{sonic,w}$ of the selected bleed models as a function of the pressure ratio p_{pl}/p_w a posteriori compared to the reference simulations

Additionally, the critical pressure ratio $p_{pl}/p_w = 0.58$ is highlighted, which depicts the required pressure ratio to obtain choked conditions. Hence, the sonic flow coefficient is assumed to be constant or at least converging for lower values. As shown in Figure 10, the bleed model of Poll et al. [3] does not follow this assumption and increases even for lower pressure ratios. Moreover, the computed sonic flow coefficient using this model becomes greater than one for ratios $p_{pl}/p_w < 0.40$, which is unphysical. Besides, a significant difference between the models validated with and without external flow is apparent. The models of Poll et al. [3], Frink et al. [5], and Grzelak et al. [8] predict significantly higher sonic flow coefficients, especially for large pressure ratios.

Interestingly, the models of Harloff and Smith [1] and Doerffer and Bohning [4] show almost the same trend for pressure ratios higher than the critical pressure ratio, even though their approaches are entirely different. Below the critical ratio, the models diverge as different approaches to forecast choked flow are used. The model of Abrahamson and Brower [2], one of the first introduced

Fig. 11: Prediction of the bleed mass fluxes based on physical quantities from Figure 6 for various bleed models

bleed models, estimates a notably lower bleed flow, which is a consequence of the empirically derived constant $c_b = 0.2$.

Moreover, the sonic flow coefficients obtained from the reference simulations are plotted for the throat ratios $TR = 0.3, 0.7$, and 1.3 . The values obtained for $TR = 0.7$ are marked in red. It can be shown that the bleed model of Slater [6] fits best with the reference data.

All bleed models are a posteriori applied to the reference data from the previous Subsection and illustrated in Figure 11 to evaluate their accuracy. As expected, the models validated without external flow overestimate the bleed mass flux along the entire bleed region. The best fitting is the model of Slater [6], which is not surprising as it is based on experimental data on supersonic turbulent boundary bleeding. Interestingly, the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4] underestimates the bleed mass flux for small holes and overestimates it for large holes. This difference is attributed to the wall shear stress, which is used as input in this model and is twice as high for the small hole diameter as for the larger hole. Thus, relying on the wall shear stress seems to be unsuitable in a bleed model.

Please note that the model of Harloff and Smith [1] is not shown in Figure 11 as it requires the Mach number at the boundary layer edge. The automatic extraction of this value is challenging, if not impossible, because of the complexity of the flow field around the holes.

5.1.2 Implementation as boundary condition

In the next step, the bleed models were implemented and applied as a boundary condition in the RANS-solver. For the simulation with the porous bleed boundary condition, the mesh was simplified and consisted only of one cell in

Fig. 12: Influence of the mesh resolution

the spanwise direction, as illustrated in Figure 3b. A mesh convergence study was performed to determine the influence on the mass flux along the bleed region and the downstream velocity profiles. The mesh spacing was varied from $\Delta x = 0.25$ mm to $\Delta x = 2.00$ mm. As shown in Figure 12, the influence of the spatial resolution is small in the case without a shock-boundary layer interaction. Only at the beginning of the plate (see Figure 12a) minor differences in the bleed mass flux are notable as pressure gradients are smeared with lower mesh resolutions. However, the nominal mesh with a spacing of $\Delta x = 0.5$ mm (80 cells along the porous bleed region) overlays almost perfectly with the fine grid and is considered converged. Altogether, the total mesh size was reduced to less than 0.1 M. cells when applying the boundary condition.

Figure 13 shows, like Figure 5, the Mach number contours for the models of Slater [6] and Grzelak et al. [8]. Since both models do not consider the hole diameter, the outcome is independent of the hole diameter. Thus, any hole diameter effects, as a difference in the effectiveness regarding the thinning of the boundary layer, are not predicted by the models.

The observation of Figures 13a and 13b reveals an impact of the model on the effectiveness. By applying the model of Grzelak et al. [8], the thinning of the boundary layer is more marked. This can be seen by the stronger expansion fan at the beginning of the plate leading to higher Mach numbers outside the boundary layer and higher momentum in the vicinity of the wall at the end of the plate.

Compared to Figure 5, a significant difference between the boundary condition and the reference simulation becomes apparent. Since the suction occurs over all the cells and not only through locally distributed holes (see Figure 3), local flow phenomena such as the expansion fans and barrier shocks generated by the holes are not reflected. Only the expansion fan at the beginning and the trailing shock at the end of the plate are present.

Fig. 13: Mach number contours for the applied bleed boundary condition

More details of the flow along the bleed region are plotted in Figure 14. Figure 14a shows that the wall pressure is underestimated for all models, except the model of Abrahamson and Brower [2], which should lead to an underestimation of the bleed mass flow rate since the pressure ratio p_{pl}/p_w is increased. By looking at the bleed mass flux (Figure 14b), similar results to Figure 11 are found. The models of Slater [6] and Choe et al. [7] show the best agreement with the reference data. Moreover, the model of Harloff and Smith [1] is close to the reference simulations. The models of Poll et al. [3], Frink et al. [5], and Grzelak et al. [8] overestimate the mass flux as expected. However, the values are lower than in the a posteriori comparison as the external wall pressure is underestimated (see Figure 14a). In contrast, applying the model of Abrahamson and Brower [2] leads to the same results as in the a posteriori calculation, as the external wall pressure is almost identical.

In Figure 14c, the wall shear stresses predicted by the bleed models are compared to that of the reference cases. The wall shear stress is interesting as it allows the assessment of the flow momentum in the wall vicinity. Moreover, it is used by the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4]. Applying the bleed boundary condition induces high wall shear stresses independently of the model compared to those extracted from the reference simulations. The higher the predicted bleed mass flux of the model, the higher the wall shear stress.

Special attention must be drawn to the fact that the overestimation of the wall shear stress does not necessarily mean an overestimation of the modeled drag force on the bleed patch. Pressure drag forces caused by the bleed holes are not considered in the bleed modeling. In order to assess the drag prediction capability of the models, we computed the overall drag (dotted lines in

Fig. 14: Applied boundary condition compared to the reference simulations

Fig. 14c) consisting of friction and pressure losses for the reference simulations and compared it to the friction drag obtained from the simulations with the bleed boundary condition. Similar trends for the total drag in the reference simulations compared to the friction drag using the boundary condition is apparent. For a clearer comparison, the drag forces per unit area for the whole bleed region are illustrated in Figure 15 for all these cases.

The first look at the first two bars in Figure 15 reveals a significantly larger amount of pressure drag in the reference simulations compared to friction drag. The pressure drag is induced by the flow into the bleed holes resulting in a strong force on the hole's rear wall. Additionally, the flow separation in the front increases the pressure drag. Contrary to the friction drag, the pressure drag is higher for larger holes since the captured stream tube increases, resulting in a higher flow momentum streaming into the holes. The drag force computed for the simulations using the bleed boundary condition consists only of the friction drag since the wall is perfectly smooth and aligned with the free-stream flow. Similar to Figure 14, a clear variation between the models is notable. The higher the estimated suction mass flux, the higher the

Fig. 15: Drag force per unit area computed for the case of supersonic turbulent boundary layer bleeding

friction force as the flow momentum in the wall vicinity increases. Surprisingly, the total drag computed is in the same order of magnitude as the drag obtained from the reference simulations, although the bleed models have not been explicitly derived or calibrated for this purpose. However, the models with the best prediction of the bleed mass flux underestimate the total drag force by approximately 30% to 40%.

The high friction drag can be associated with fuller boundary layer profiles downstream of the bleed region, as shown in Figure 14d. Moreover, the figure shows the inadequate modeling of the hole diameter influence on the boundary layer profile, which is not considered by the bleed models. The observation of fuller boundary layer profiles downstream of the bleed region matches the findings of Baurle and Norris [20]. In their study, the experiments of Willis et al. [16] were simulated using the bleed models of Doerffer and Bohning [4] and Slater [6] and compared to the experimental data. The plate length was relatively short, with approximately three boundary layer thicknesses compared to the plate length in our study ($L_w \approx 9.5\delta_{99}$). Thus, more significant deviations obtained in our study are expectable. Other studies [6, 7] did not focus on the boundary layer profiles but only on contour fields. However, a closer look at their data also shows a significantly higher momentum close to the wall downstream of the bleed region compared to the upstream flow.

Figure 16 shows boundary layer profiles 10 mm downstream of the bleed region and the inflow profile in dimensionless units for velocity and wall distance. Again, a difference between the boundary condition and reference simulations is apparent. If the bleed models are implemented in the boundary condition, the slope of the dimensionless velocity is greater than $\frac{1}{\kappa} \ln y^+$ in the overlap layer, corresponding to an overestimation of the velocity. In contrast,

Fig. 16: Comparison of the boundary layers downstream of the plate in dimensionless numbers

the boundary layers extracted from the reference simulation fit with the inflow profile in this region, meaning the slope is not increased.

We now discuss the influence of the way the bleed working regime is set. As stated in Section 3.3, three options to apply the boundary condition have been implemented. Figure 17 compares these three models applied for the methods of Slater [6], which shows a good fit with the reference simulations regarding the bleed mass flux, and Grzelak et al. [8], which overestimates the mass flux. The plenum pressure p_{pl} and the bleed mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl} are extracted from the reference simulation with $D = 2$ mm and applied to the models. While the bleed mass flow rate is measured directly at the plenum outlet, the plenum pressure is acquired by averaging the static pressure on a slice inside the cavity plenum with a distance of three hole diameters from the hole exits.

As all bleed models rely on the plenum pressure p_{pl} to compute the bleed mass flux, applying this option is assumed to be the closest to the a posteriori comparison (see Section 5.1.1). A view in Figure 17b proves this assumption since the mass flux predicted by the model of Grzelak et al. [8] is closer to that of the a posteriori comparison. However, its value is slightly lower due to the underestimated external wall pressure (see Figure 17a). The same effect also leads to an underestimation of the bleed mass flux using the model of Slater [6].

Consequently, it must be stated that the higher effectiveness of the boundary condition leads to an underestimated wall mass flux for all models. Since

Fig. 17: Comparison of the different bleed options for the models of Slater [6] and Grzelak et al. [8]

the thinning of the boundary layer is enhanced, the expansion fan at the beginning of the plate is strengthened. Thus, the static wall pressure is lower. In other words, a bleed model, which fits the reality perfectly in a posteriori comparison, will predict a lower bleed mass flux when implemented as a boundary condition and produce a fuller profile.

In contrast, fixing the bleed mass flow rate correctly estimates the bleed mass flux. Nevertheless, slight deviations between the models and the reference simulations, and also between the models, are notable. While the application of the model of Slater [6] prognosticates an almost constant mass flux along the plate, the model of Grzelak et al. [8] predicts a positive slope. Fixing the bleed mass flow rate also results in similar trends of the external wall pressure, the wall shear stress, and the boundary layer profile downstream of the plate for both models.

The default used option of a fixed throat ratio TR always gives an outcome between the other options since both bleed mass flow rate and plenum pressure are related to the throat area of the exit nozzle. Larger ratios result in a larger

bleed volume flow rate and, thus, in a lower plenum pressure. However, with the decreasing plenum pressure, the density and, as a result, the mass flow rate decrease.

Moreover, a high deviation in the outcome of the different options highlights the inaccuracy of a model. For the model of Slater [6], all three options lead to the same results. In contrast, the options significantly impact the performance of the model of Grzelak et al. [8]. Fixing the mass flow rate results in an overestimated plenum pressure, whereas fixing the plenum pressure leads to an overestimated bleed mass flow rate.

5.2 Shock-boundary layer interaction control

5.2.1 A posteriori comparison

Based on the extracted physical quantities from Figure 9, the bleed mass fluxes using the bleed models are computed and shown in Figure 18 as for the previous case. A clear distinction between the models validated with and without external flow can be made again. The models of Poll et al. [3], Frink et al. [5], and Grzelak et al. [8], which are not validated with the external flow, overestimate the mass flux. The relative deviation to the reference simulations is more significant in the supersonic region upstream of the incident shock than in subsonic conditions.

Fig. 18: Analytical computed bleed mass fluxes based on physical quantities from Figure 9

In contrast, the purely supersonic validated bleed models, such as the model of Slater [6], underestimate the bleed mass flux for subsonic conditions.

All models except the model of Abrahamson and Brower [2] overestimate the bleed mass flux upstream of the shock, where the pressure difference from the external wall to the cavity plenum, and consequently the mass flux, is low. Altogether, the models of Doerffer and Bohning [4] and Choe et al. [7] fit best. However, the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4] fits better for the hole diameter of $D = 2.0$ mm because the wall shear stress is lower than for small holes. For the same reason as in the previous section, the model of Harloff and Smith [1] is not considered in this comparison.

5.2.2 Implementation as boundary condition

Equal to the first flow case, a mesh convergence study was performed. Again, the mesh spacing was varied from $\Delta x = 0.25$ mm to $\Delta x = 2.00$ mm. Due to higher pressure gradients caused by the incident shock, the influence of the mesh is more visible. As illustrated in Figure 19a, a lower spatial resolution leads to a smearing of the bleed mass flux in the region of the shock foot. The finer the mesh, the steeper the rise of the bleed mass flux. However, the difference between regular and fine mesh is negligible. Also, the downstream velocity profiles (see Figure 19b) reveal a minor influence of the mesh. The coarser the mesh, the fuller the velocity profiles. This artifact of the smeared shock results in a lower adverse pressure gradient and hence, a smaller effect on the flow.

Figure 20 illustrates the flow field around the bleed region for the models of Slater [6] and Grzelak et al. [8]. Here, the model of Slater [6] shows a good agreement with the reference simulations even though the bleed mass flux is generally underestimated in the subsonic region. In contrast, applying the model of Grzelak et al. [8] overestimates the bleed mass flux and, hence, the removal of the low-momentum flow. Downstream of the shock, the Mach

Fig. 19: Influence of the mesh resolution

Fig. 20: Mach number contour fields for the applied boundary condition

number in the vicinity of the wall is significantly higher, which results in a stronger trailing shock at the end of the plate.

Another observation from applying the bleed boundary condition is the low upstream influence of the shock wave since the subsonic fraction of the boundary layer is quasi-non-existent. The shock reflection looks inviscid without any flow separation, which is more notable for the model of Grzelak et al. [8].

A deeper comparison of the bleed models with the reference simulations is shown in Figure 21, where the wall pressure, the bleed mass flux, the wall shear stress, and the boundary layer profiles are compared. A view at Figure 21a reveals substantial differences between the models. The location of the shock, which is the position of the steepest pressure gradient, significantly differs between the models. The shock is located at 60% of the plate length if the model of Abrahamson and Brower [2] is applied and at 72% for the model of Grzelak et al. [8]. The reason for such a discrepancy is the higher estimated mass removal (see Figure 21b). Moreover, the pressure rise induced by the shock is increased if the mass flux is underestimated because the flow deflection along the shock simultaneously decreases. For large mass fluxes, the flow is bent towards the wall, inducing a higher deflection angle, and the shock intensity is consequently weaker. However, this effect results in a stronger trailing shock at the end of the plate, which is visible with the higher external wall pressure near the end of the porous plate.

Fig. 21: Applied boundary condition compared to the reference simulations with shock-boundary layer interaction

In the next step, we compare the predicted wall shear stress with those of the reference simulations (see Figure 21c) to assess the boundary layer state along the bleed region and as input for the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4]. The higher the predicted mass flux, the higher the wall shear stress downstream of the shock. Contrary to the reference simulations, the wall shear stress rises below the shock foot for all models except those of Abrahamson and Brower [2] and Doerffer and Bohning [4]. Again, a distinction must be drawn between wall shear stress and drag force (illustrated by the dotted line in Figure 21c), as pressure forces acting inside the holes are not considered. Surprisingly, the trend of the wall shear stress is similar to that of the total drag force, including the pressure drag.

Contrary to the first case, the overestimation of the wall shear stress is not associated with significantly fuller boundary layer profiles downstream of the porous plate (see Figure 21d). We assume that the more intense trailing shock and the expansion fan generated by the rear edge of the shock generator result in a homogenization of the boundary layer.

Fig. 22: Drag force per unit area computed for the case with shock-boundary layer interaction

Similarly, as for the supersonic boundary layer bleeding, we compare the overall drag force in Figure 22. Again, the first two bars show both friction and pressure drag for the reference simulations. Like in the previous flow case, the pressure drag is more significant than the friction drag. The total drag is slightly lower than in the first flow case. All the applied models underestimate the drag compared to the reference overall drag. The overestimation of the friction drag is insufficient to compensate for the absence of any pressure drag. Moreover, the variation between the bleed models is minor compared to the first flow case.

The influence of using the different options on the outcome of the models is shown in Figure 23. Again, the models of Slater [6] and Grzelak et al. [8] are chosen. In general, the same conclusion as in Section 5.1 for supersonic turbulent boundary layer bleeding can be made. The most interesting is the application of the fixed bleed mass flow rate \dot{m}_{bl} . If the mass flow rate is equal for both models, the shock position is the same, as visible in the static pressure curves (Figure 23a), as well as the boundary layer profiles downstream of the bleed region (Figure 23d). However, the model of Grzelak et al. [8] underestimates the bleed mass flux in the supersonic and overestimates that in the subsonic region. The opposite trend is seen in the model of Slater [6].

Fig. 23: Comparison of the different bleed options for the models of Slater [6] and Grzelak et al. [8]

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we have evaluated the prediction accuracy of state-of-the-art porous bleed models, which have been implemented in the in-house RANS-solver *elsA*. Two reference cases, which have been selected for their practical interest, were simulated to assess the accuracy of the applied bleed models and to show the model deficiencies on different plate geometries. The models have partially shown significant differences in predicting the bleed mass flux along the plate.

For the turbulent supersonic boundary layer bleeding, the reference simulations demonstrated an influence of the hole diameter on the flow. None of the models considers this effect in the computation of the bleed mass flux. However, the model of Slater [6] fits well with the reference simulation in an a posteriori comparison. Remarkably, the model of Doerffer and Bohning [4] underestimates the bleed mass flux for small hole diameters and overestimates it for large diameters because of the wall shear stress used in the model.

Implementing the bleed models as a blowing/suction boundary condition reveals more significant deviations from the reference simulations. The boundary condition, applied on all patch cells, leads to a more substantial boundary layer thinning, which results in high wall shear stresses and significantly fuller boundary layer profiles downstream of the bleed region compared to the reference simulations. As a consequence of the overpredicted thinning effect, the expansion fan at the beginning of the porous plate is more intense, which lowers the static wall pressure. Thus, the driving pressure difference from the external wall to the cavity, and hence, the bleed mass flux, are reduced compared to the a posteriori comparison. The non-prediction of the local flow phenomena induced by the bleed holes is assumed to be the main reason for the deviation between the boundary condition and reference simulations.

The same observations have been made for the second flow case with the shock-boundary layer interaction. The implementation of the bleed models as a boundary condition results in a seemingly inviscid interaction. No flow separation is apparent, and the wall shear stress below the shock foot increases contrary to the reference simulations. However, the fit of the extracted boundary layer profiles downstream of the bleed region is satisfactory but improvable. The reason is probably the existence of the trailing shock caused by the porous bleed and the expansion fan generated by the shock generator.

Altogether, no model is suitable for the shock-boundary layer interaction control. Most models are not valid for both subsonic and supersonic flow. Moreover, essential parameters, such as the bleed hole diameter, are not considered and lead to substantial deviations. Besides, applying suction on all patch cells results in an overpredicted flow control by the boundary condition, making the appearance of a flow separation almost impossible.

However, the models of Slater [6] and Choe et al. [7] provide a good fit for a posteriori predictions of the bleed mass flow rate for supersonic flow. Moreover, applying a bleed model for a fixed mass flow rate gives an indication of the effect on the shock-boundary layer interaction, even though the calculated plenum pressure can significantly differ from reality.

Future work is required to improve the modeling accuracy by capturing local flow phenomena. We expect that could improve the prediction capabilities of the effectiveness of the porous bleed system. Important geometrical parameters such as the hole diameter, but also length-to-diameter ratio or hole pattern should be considered in a new model. Moreover, the model must be trimmed to work not only when applied a posteriori but also when implemented as a boundary condition in a RANS solver.

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Declarations

Competing interests. The authors declare no competing interests.

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